

STUDIES ON THE ENZYMES OF THE SEEDS OF *BUTEA FRONDOSA*. PART II. LIPOLYTIC ENZYME.

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The fresh seeds of *Butea frondosa* were found to contain a lipolytic enzyme in addition to the proteolytic enzyme reported earlier. Its action has been studied in substrates like olive oil, castor oil and rape seed oil and it acts on all of these equally well. The lipase seems to act best in a slightly alkaline medium and shows an optimum temperature of about 40°. The aqueous emulsions of the raw seeds as well as that of the defatted seeds act equally well.

In the previous part of this paper (This Journal, p. 101) it was mentioned that a proteolytic enzyme and a lipolytic enzyme have been observed by us in the seeds of *Butea frondosa* and that there is no mention about these in the seeds in the literature. In studying the details of the lipase action, we followed mainly the methods of Willstätter and Waldschmidt-Leitz used in the study of *Ricinus lipase* (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 161).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Defatted Seeds.—The finely powdered seeds were treated with six times the weight of carbon tetrachloride and vigorously shaken in a flask for some time. The solid material was then filtered by suction and washed first with carbon tetrachloride and then with ether. It was then dried in a vacuum desiccator and stored in a bottle.

Preliminary Experiments with Defatted Seeds.—Olive oil (2.5 g.), defatted seeds (2.5 g.), phosphate buffer of p_H 7 (2 c.c.) were shaken vigorously in a flask for 3 minutes and then kept in an incubator at 37° for 20 hours. The mixture was then treated with an excess of alcohol and ether to stop the lipase action and titrated with *N*/10-caustic potash using phenolphthalein as indicator. A control experiment was also carried out without the use of the seed powder. The results showed strong lipolytic action but as they were not uniform the experiments were repeated with the use of an enzyme extract prepared as shown below.

Preparation of Aqueous Emulsion of Enzyme.—This was always prepared fresh by treating defatted seeds (10 g.) with distilled water (60 c.c.) added in

small portions and rubbed intimately in a mortar. The cream was pressed out through muslin and the residue again treated in the same manner with 60 c. c. of distilled water and pressed out. The total extract amounted to 100 c. c.

Method of Estimation.—The substrate oil (2.5 g.) was weighed out in a small conical flask and mixed with the enzyme extract equivalent to 1 g. of the defatted seeds with the addition of 2 c. c. of a phosphate buffer. The contents of the flask were thoroughly mixed, kept in a thermostat at 37° for several hours. The mixture was then treated with 95% alcohol (30 c. c.) and ether (15 c. c.) and titrated with *N*/10-alcoholic potash using phenolphthalein as indicator. As the colour of phenolphthalein was rather quickly discharged, the end-point was noted immediately when the colour of the mixture became distinctly red. A control experiment without the enzyme extract was done in every case. The difference in the amount of *N*/10-alcoholic potash required gave a measure of the lipase action. The percentage of saponification was calculated (not shown) according to the following formula of Willstätter and Waldschmidt-Leitz:—

$$\text{Percentage of saponification} = \frac{V \times 56.1 \times 100}{W \times S}$$

where *V* is the volume of *N*-caustic potash; *W* the weight and *S* the saponification value of the oil taken. In an actual experiment, where 100 c. c. of extract, equivalent to 1 g. of defatted seeds, was allowed to act for 20 hours at 37° on 2.5 g. of olive oil in the presence of phosphate buffer of *p*_n 8, the alkali required for the main experiment was 12.5 c.c. and that for the control 5.7 c. c. of *N*/10-caustic potash.

$$\text{Hence, percentage of saponification} = \frac{0.68 \times 56.1 \times 100}{2.5 \times 190} = 8.9\%$$

In the Tables I—IV, 10 c. c. of aqueous emulsion of seeds (unless otherwise mentioned) equivalent to 1 g. of seed and phosphate buffer (2 c. c.) have been used at a temperature, of 37°. Hydrolysis has been expressed in terms of c. c. of *N*/10-KOH.

TABLE I.

Substrate=2.5 g. of olive oil (raw seed).

<i>p</i> _n	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0
Hydrolysis after 20 hours	4.8	5.1	6.4	6.8

TABLE II.

Substrate = 2.5 g. of olive oil.

p_H	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0
Hydrolysis after 20 hrs	4.9	5.9	6.1	7.2

TABLE III.

Substrate = 2.5 g. of castor oil.

p_H	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0
Hydrolysis after 20 hrs.	5.4	5.4	6.2	7.0

TABLE IV.

Substrate = 2.5 g. of rape seed oil.

p_H	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0
Hydrolysis after 20 hrs.	4.7	4.8	5.7	6.4

The results in the above tables show that the optimum reaction of the medium is a p_H of about 8.

TABLE V.

Study of Optimum Temperature.

Substrate = 2.5 g. of olive oil. 10 C. c. of aqueous emulsion of the seed equivalent to 1 g. of defatted seeds. Phosphate buffer at p_H 8. Incubation period 3 hours.

Temperature	...	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°
Hydrolysis	...	1.8	2.9	1.6	0.7	0.3

The maximum hydrolysis seems to take place at 40°; the reaction of the mixture being at its optimum p_H 8.